

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Technology Based Microchip implanted in human Health Monitoring and Tracking

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) technology is a broad field which has greater impact on people, communities, and society with substantial implications for humanity. Artificial intelligence makes machine smarter. AI measures are designed to empower people to build their trust and practice their use in real-time application. The new devices are invented with AI technology progresses with time. Microchip is an integrated semiconductor circuit which began as a controller to perform specific task. Microchips have been progressively curtailed to the point where they can fit on a fingertip. New types of chips are being developed to achieve advances in AI by embracing deep neural networks for voice recognition and image processing. The microchips handle data in different way from the silicon logic circuits to hardware for decades.

Keywords: Human Health, Implanted, Microchip, RFID tag.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microchip use RFID tag for transmission and reception which has integrated circuit to store data and antenna for reception and transmitting signals between that circuit and reader. AI based microchip provides unprecedented access to the capacities of data required to design chips optimized to run them.[2] The microchip broadcast electromagnetic signal with associated reader that any RFID chip within its signal range and frequency will respond with an encrypted signal that is decoded by the reader. Microchips are changing everyone's life. It can be used in homes, ATM, transportation, machinery, security even it can be implanted in human and animal bodies to monitor their health and activity. Microchip offers a better interaction with machine world. Microchips offer immeasurable uses in multidisciplinary field of engineering and technology areas.

II. MICROCHIP IN HEALTH MONITORING AND TRACKING

AI based microchip applications increase the health results and value of life for millions of people in recent years. Microchip can be injected to the individuals which keeps track of their health system. For patients, even it could able to detect the tumor at faster rate instead of waiting for days to get their result. It can be used to gain quick access to the patient medical records and it can be implant to the person who is suffering from heart disease and diabetics. Even hospital equipment can be tracked using RFID microchip. Fig.1 illustrates microchip implanted in human muscles to prevent health disorders. Health issue is not a primary concern if microchips have been used.

Fig.1 Micro Chipping In Human finger

III. MICROCHIP IMPLANTED IN PET

Previously pet owners would add collar tags for their PET. Currently many pet owners are implant microchips for their pet to track them if they were lost, monitor their health status continuously and it can act as travel assistance if pets were boarded in flight.

IV. HUMAN MICRO CHIPPING

Now-a-days many people are implanting microchips under their skin. Those chips contain information about individual identification and other personal details. It can be better benefit for child and elderly safety. [3] There is no need to carry driving license, atm cards , start the vehicle without keys, play music based on individual preference. Fig(1) states That information can be stored in those chips even people can pay through the chip just by waving their hands. Micro chipping criminals enhance law enforcement which helps police to track down the criminals if they escaped from the prison.

Fig.2 Micro Chipping In Human Muscle

Microchip takes the automation to next level by opening the car door if a person is in front of the car, switching on to favorite television channel, automatically control the home appliances. The RFID tag installed in vehicle or in home is connected to the controller which enhances the autonomous operation.[4]

V. MICROCHIP IN WORKPLACE

In some workplace microchip has been deployed in employees to be used in place of ID cards, monitoring their work completion process and for their salary payment. [5]The companies may track the movement of the employees.

VI. CONS OF MICROCHIP

Implanted RFID microchip has various disadvantages which concern both health and privacy.

Microchip Pose threat to health

The effect of microchip is not known if it stays for longer in a person's body. It may not stay in same place, it may migrate to different place which makes it hard to find especially in case of any medical emergencies and other issues like electrical threats, detrimental tissue reactions, infections and inconsistency with medical equipment.[6] There is possibility of nerve damage in case of dental implant which may cause serious effects.

Data Leaks

Microchip has sensitive information about individuals. Embedding so much personal information on a single chip make a person prime target for hackers.[7] The information fed in the chip is not only readable but also writable i.e. personal information can be corrupted and alter the person data without their knowledge.

VII. CONCLUSION

Microchip has power to kill an individual. The microchip may get affected by other medical device which may spread virus. It may take the peoples freedom of choice. Someone may eavesdrop, modify and corrupt a person's data. Microchip implant is a digital interaction tool which concerns both benefit and drawbacks. With microchip implant it's not possible to ride bus for free, any theft, no excuse to go to work late, we should be on our best behavior. This technology improves over time with better feature. Microchips implanted in human is about to make a foremost upsurge in the cognizance of the human mind.

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